

ENSURING EXCESSIVE PRESSURE RESISTANCE IN IMPROVED CONNECTING STRUCTURES**Hamidova G.***Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Phd. Scholar***ABSTRACT**

The issue of ensuring a safe working regime is one of the main urgent issues facing the modern world. Industrial facilities have a wide variety. According to their work functions and constructions of each type, different number of connecting structures are used in their composition. The connecting structures used in the industry are divided into drawers, connecting taps and valves. The causes of their failure are generally united in the issue of pressure resistance. The research work is devoted to the issue of pressure resistance of the improved drawer construction, which is included in the class of connecting structures. The conditioning condition of the proposed structure was defined, and as a result of theoretical and experimental experiments, the conditioning condition of the structure was calculated. An improved new drawer structure was proposed, based on the solidworks program of the proposed structure, 3D simulation tests of its body's resistance to excess pressure were carried out, and the safety functionality of the drawer was confirmed.

Also, the shaping condition of the drawer stopper node was determined and as a result of the calculation, it was found that the proposed drawer structure fully satisfies the shaping condition.

It has been found that the improved drawer construction has a safe working process.

Keywords: Improved draw, pressure resistance, body, binding structure.

Introduction: The safe working process of manifold systems and devices in industrial enterprises directly depends on the issue of pressure resistance of connecting structures. Pressure stability issues are checked by means of special tests in each of the prepared connecting structures and evaluated according to the reserve factor. The issue of ensuring a safe working regime is one of the main urgent issues facing the modern world. Industrial facilities have a wide variety. According to their work functions and constructions of each type, different number of connecting structures are used in their composition. For example, it can be said that between 350-500 different types of connecting structures are used in one unit in oil refining enterprises. Ensuring the safe operation of the connecting structures used in these devices ensures the safety of the device as a whole [2-6, 9].

The safe operation of connecting structures depends on their rejection. These refusals can be mainly divided into 3 places.

1. Refusal of metal metal parts
2. Rejection of metal rubber parts
3. Rejection of rubber rubber parts

The occurrence of refusals leads to the loss of functionality of the device. At the same time, it can be said that there are such connecting structures that prevent accidents by ensuring complete closure of the system unit during dangerous situations occurring in the unit. In such cases, failure of the connecting structure leads to the emergence of real accident conditions [7-10].

The safety criterion of connecting structures appears when the issue of their resistance to working pressure is not properly resolved.

Considering this point of view, the purpose of the research work is to develop and test a drawer structure with a safe working mode and the possibility of fully closing the system block in case of leaks.

To solve the problem, a new drawer structure with high security capability was proposed. The new drawer construction is provided with an additional mechanism

to ensure complete closure of the product in case of leakage in the drawer itself in dangerous situations [1].

The proposed structure belongs to the drawer, which is the main type of connecting structures, and is intended for the management and regulation of liquid and gas flow in various fields of industry, especially in the oil industry. The conducted studies show that the drawer's locking details are its most quickly damaged details, increasing the wear resistance of these details and facilitating their reparability in working mode are urgent issues. Also, it is a major problem to replace the parts and joints of the drawer without maintaining its function (1). The solution to this problem is global.

To solve this problem, results were obtained on the available 3MC-65x35 drawer (1). Said drawer consists of a slide, a shield, a spindle, a tray spring, a cushion cover, a set screw, a finger, a pin, a saddle, a clamping element, a pressure ring, a support ring, a cuff, a washer, a plate, a plug and a body.

The most functional details of this drawer are its airtight details. The elastic conditioning (hermetic) details of the drawer quickly get tired and fail due to the aggressive environment as a result of the deformation caused by the change of the working pressure force. When the metal-to-metal or rubber elements that create hermeticity fail, it is impossible to change the details of the drawer without saving the work. Job retention causes economic loss as it leads to work stoppages. One of the problems is the development of drawers that allow changing the elastic elements of the drawer without saving the work.

The purpose of the work: development and testing of a drawer construction with high hermeticity and control, with the ability to change the details of the fittings under pressure without maintaining the working mode

The essence of the work: It is the creation of a drawer structure with high security capabilities and resistant to eating. One of the possibilities of this construction is that it has the possibility to change its switches in working mode.

The novelty of the work: the proposed design has a mechanism to shut down the system in dangerous situations and during repairs. The mechanism attached to the plugging node of the drain completely cuts off the connection between its passage throat and the spindle-nut node, ensuring smooth movement of the liquid inside the drain.

As a result, since the spindle nut node of the drawer is free from fluid pressure, it becomes possible to disassemble it and replace its parts. Buda ensures easy replacement of its styling elements when the drawer is working.

As a result of the durability reports of the construction proposed by us, it was found that the drawer fulfills the condition of workability.

The following given condition must be satisfied between the performance test of the improved drawer and its theoretical solutions.

$$q_{kt} \leq q_{kn} \leq [q_{sb}]$$

Here, q_{kt} - the minimum value of the relative pressure at the exit of the drawer is determined by experiment when the drawer is closed.

q_{kn} is the relative contact pressure of the working pressure at the outlet side of the drawer, it is determined theoretically.

q_{sb} - the value of the relative pressure generated by the liquid at the outlet when the drawer is closed.

The conditioning condition of the improved drawer structure is defined by the following condition on experimental and theoretical basis.

$$50\text{MPa} \leq 70\text{MPa} \leq 120\text{MPa}$$

The received price satisfies the conditioning condition. This condition determines the sealing factor. But in the matter of pressure resistance, the guarantee of safety is the pressure resistance test of the body. The proposed structure should be pressure resistant even in the event of an abnormal situation.

The body of the improved drawer construction is pressure simulated. Figure 1 shows the pressure distribution simulation.

Fig. 1. Simulation of pressure distribution inside the drawer

The pressure distribution inside the body is simulated with the drawer closed.

Since the body is fully exposed to pressure in a closed state, the simulation was conducted in a closed state (Fig. 1). It can be seen from the graph that the pressure has a maximum value in the part of the body where the fluid passes. This means that the pressure will create maximum effect on the stopper knot. Mainly shield or disc, saddle and clamping nodes are subjected

to pressure in the jamming knot. That is, since metal-to-metal and metal-rubber moldings are carried out in these nodes, the failure of these nodes can lead to the failure of the drawer. But this causes leaks. The pressure resistance of the body is a more serious issue in terms of safety. The conducted simulation process proves that the proposed structure is resistant to extra pressure (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2. Pressure distribution graph inside the drawer.

The proposed structure is suitable for application as the main connecting structure of the devices in the oil refining chemical industry, in nuclear power plants and compressor stations, as well as for setting the system to close the system remotely in advance prevention of dangers.

A special feature of this construction is that the rubber cuffs can be changed during the use of devices. The fact that the drawer has such a feature leads to an extension of the time between their repairs. In other words, the rubber cuffs of the drawers whose cuffs are out of order will be replaced before the work is stopped.

The result

1. An improved new drawer construction was proposed, based on the solidworks program of the proposed construction, 3D simulation tests of its body's resistance to excess pressure were conducted and the safety functionality of the drawer was confirmed.

2. The condition for shaping the locking knot of the drawer was determined and as a result of the calculation, it was found that the proposed drawer structure fully satisfied the shaping condition.

References

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